

The 20th International Conference on Open Repositories

Chicago, Illinois, USA | June 15-18, 2025

Conference Agenda

Session Overview

Date: Sunday, 15/June/2025

09:00 - 16:00	Registration and Refreshments Location: Rogers Lobby	
09:30 - 12:30	DSpace Developer Meet-Up and Q&A Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Yves Vincent Grossmann , Goethe University DSpace Developer Meet-Up and Q&A <u>Tim Donohue</u>¹, <u>Holger Lenz</u>¹, <u>Pascal Becker</u>² 1: Lyrasis, United States of America; 2: The Library Code, Germany	
09:30 - 17:00	DSpace SEO and Statistics Master Class Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Elizabeth Krznarich , University of Wisconsin DSpace SEO and Statistics Master Class <u>Bram Luyten</u> Atmire, Belgium	InvenioRDM Workshop Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Matt Carson , Northwestern University InvenioRDM Workshop <u>Matthew B. Carson</u>¹, <u>Steven Eardley</u>², <u>Sara Gonzales</u>¹, <u>Richard Jones</u>², <u>Hrafn Malmquist</u>², <u>Aaron McCollough</u>³, <u>Maximilian Moser</u>⁴, <u>Kate Pechekhonova</u>⁵, <u>Chokri Ben Romdhane</u>⁶, <u>Pablo Tamarit</u>⁷, <u>Deb Verhoff</u>⁵, <u>Guillaume Viger</u>¹, <u>Zacharias Zacharodimos</u>⁷ 1: Northwestern University, United States of America; 2: Cottage Labs, United Kingdom; 3: Ubiquity Press, United Kingdom; 4: TU Wien, Austria; 5: New York University, United States of America; 6: CNU DST, Tunisia; 7: European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), Switzerland
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch Break (not provided- attendees responsible for their own lunch)	
14:00 - 17:00	FAIR Metadata Bright Spots: Guides on the Road to Future Possibilities Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Leigh Stork , University of Strathclyde FAIR Metadata Bright Spots: Guides on the Road to Future Possibilities <u>Ted Habermann</u>, <u>Erin Robinson</u> Metadata Game Changers, United States of America	

Date: Monday, 16/June/2025

08:00 - 17:00	Registration Location: Rogers Lobby				
09:00 - 09:40	Opening Plenary Location: Griffin Auditorium 09:00-09:05- Introduction and housekeeping 09:05-09:15- Welcome to the University of Chicago 09:15-09:30- Steering Committee welcome 09:30-09:40- Program Committee welcome				
09:40 - 10:30	Keynote speaker Heather Joseph Location: Griffin Auditorium As the Executive Director of SPARC, Heather Joseph is an internationally renowned and well-respected expert in open research policies, practices, and implementation strategies. Under her stewardship, SPARC has become the leading advocacy organization that promotes innovative, open, and equitable global systems of research and education.				
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break Location: Rogers Lobby				
11:00 - 12:00	Panel- Pushing the boundaries on citation tracking and usage reporting for open research outputs Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Emily Bongiovanni , Carnegie Mellon University Pushing the boundaries on citation tracking and usage reporting for open research outputs Iratxe Puebla¹, Maria Gould¹, John Chodacki², Pablo Tamarit³, Jamie Wittenberg⁴ 1: DataCite, United Kingdom; 2: California Digital Library; 3: Zenodo; 4: University of Colorado, Boulder				
11:00am - 12:30pm	Presentations- Repository sustainability and future-proofing Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Maureen Walsh , The Ohio State University Beyond the Buzzwords: agile collaboration and rejecting a perfectionist mindset (how we did it, and you can too!) Kate Lynch, Hector Correa, Hannah Hadley , Princeton University, United States of America Democratization of Knowledge in the Open Science Era: The Role of Free Software and the Moara Network in Scientific and Technological Innovation Rebeca dos Santos de Moura, Bernardo Dionizio Vechi, Ingrid Torres Schiessl, Diego José Macêdo, Lucas Rodrigues Costa, Milton Shintaku , Brazilian Institute of Information in Science e Technology, Brazil After more than 20 years of eScholarship...where to now Chad Nelson, Justin Gonder, Alaina Wrigley , California Digital Library, United States of America	Lightning (24x7) Presentations - Repository showcase Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Laura Vilela Rodrigues Rezende , Universidade Federal de Goiás Tracing the Footprints of Academic Research in Zambia through the Institutional Repository: A Case of the University of Zambia" Zachary Zulu ZACHARY Zulu , THE UNIVERSITY OF ZAMBIA, Zambia HAL: Strengthening Connections Between Publications, Data, and Software in the French National Open Science Ecosystem Yannick Barborini, Bénédicte Kuntziger , CCSD / CNRS, France George Eliot Scholars: (Middle)Marching Towards Open Access Eleanor Dumbill¹, Beverley Park Rilett² 1: CoSector, University of London, United	Presentations- Data Repositories 1 Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Ilkay Holt , British Library Bridging the Silos of Institutional Data Repositories: Community Collaboration and Cross-Institutional Development Mikala Narlock¹, Jake Carlson² 1: Indiana University, United States of America; 2: University at Buffalo The unification of the effort: the Swedish university RDM network Karin Westin Tikkanen , Swedish National Data Service, Sweden Advancing Indigenous Data Sovereignty through Dataverse and Local Contexts Integration SONIA BARBOSA¹, James Myers¹, Ashley Rojas² 1: Harvard University, United States of America; 2: localcontexts.org	Developer Track Session 1 Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Ianthe Sutherland , University of Edinburgh A year of Hybrid ML/AI cataloging aid in Archipelago Commons: The state, the lessons and probable future(s) explained through a real production implementation Diego Alberto Pino Navarro, Allison Sherrick , Metropolitan New York Library Council, United States of America Deploying DataFed for Scientific Data Management: Lessons Learned Theodore Samuel Beers¹, Joshua Agar¹, Chad Peiper², Jane Greenberg³, Chirayu Patel¹ 1: College of Engineering, Drexel University; 2: College of Computing & Informatics, Drexel University; 3: Metadata Research Center, Drexel University Renovation and enhancement of statistics pages in DSpace 7	

Repositories in the US Federal Funding Workflow: Lessons from the “Reasonable Costs for Public Access” Project

Lauren B Collister,
Katherine Skinner, Gail Steinhart

Invest in Open Infrastructure, United States of America

Kingdom; 2: Auburn University, United States

Digital Curation in Deposita Dados: Challenges, Solutions and the Role in Academic Rigorosity

Rene Faustino
Gabriel Junior²,
Marcel Garcia de Souza¹, Leticia

Guarany Bonetti¹,
Tatyane Guedes Martins da Silva¹,
Samile Andrea de Souza Vanz²,
Caterina Groposo Pavão²

1: Instituto Brasileiro de Informação em Ciência e Tecnologia, Brazil; 2: Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul

Managing traditional and scientific knowledge: A case study of the Takinahakỹ Center for Indigenous Higher Education at the Federal University of Goiás – Brazil

Laura Vilela
Rodrigues Rezende¹,
Geisa Muller de Campos Ribeiro¹,
Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro¹,
Cassia Oliveira¹,
Fabiano Couto Corrêa da Silva²

1: Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil; 2: Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

The Current Situation, Problems and Future Development of Institutional Repositories in China: Taking the Institutional Repository of the Chinese Academy of Sciences as an Example

Ying CUI
National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China, People's

Zhongda Zhang¹, **Le Yang**²

1: University of Oklahoma, United States of America; 2: University of Oregon, United States of America

Putting your middleware on steroids with DSpace 7+ REST API

Bram Luyten
Atmire, Belgium

Jetstream2 and Cloud-Based Dev Tools for Data Curation Training

Seth Erickson
University of California, Santa Barbara

		Republic of			
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch Break Location: Rogers Lobby				
12:45pm - 1:30pm	Welcome to First-Time Attendees! Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Torsten Reimer , University of Chicago Convener: Elizabeth Krznarich , University of Wisconsin				
13:30 - 15:00	Presentations- Standards, Accessibility and Digital Preservation Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Kristi Park , Texas Digital Library, USA Building a Digital Preservation Service Model for Canadian Institutional Repositories Through Community Engagement Leanne Olson ¹ , Julia Gilmore ² , Julie Shi ² 1: Western University, Canada; 2: Scholars Portal IIIF at one end, OCFI at the other, Fedora in the middle. Claire Knowles ¹ , Tom Crane ² , Karen Abel ¹ 1: University of Leeds, United Kingdom; 2: Digirati, United Kingdom Embedding Accessibility into ETD Workflows: A Case Study Carmen Mitchell , Amy Carpenter California State University San Marcos, United States of America Practice research as a lens to enable a future with a FAIRer, more equitable scholarly research landscape Jenny Evans ¹ , Adam Vials Moore ² , Eleanor Dumbill ³ , Rory McNicholl ³ , Claire Knowles ⁴ 1: University of Westminster, United Kingdom; 2: Jisc, United Kingdom; 3: CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom; 4: University of Leeds, United Kingdom	Presentations- Citations, Tracking and Impact Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Emily Bongiovanni , Carnegie Mellon University Citations growth for journal articles that are in open digital repositories Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo ¹ , Thiago Magela Dias ² , Marcel Garcia de Souza ¹ 1: Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; 2: Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil New Applications for measuring Data Impact in a Domain Science Open Repository Joshua Freeze , Maria Esteva , James Carson University of Texas at Austin, United States of America; Texas Advance Computing Center Enhancing Repository Integration with Crossref Services Johanssen Odhiambo Obanda , Amanda French Crossref Interoperability between Digital Repositories and OpenAlex: Challenges and Strategies Marcel Garcia de Souza ¹ , Thiago Magela Dias ² , Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo ¹ 1: Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; 2:	Presentations- Metadata and Harvesting Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Joseph Kraus , Colorado School of Mines SDG-Classify: Automating the classification of research outputs into UN SDGs Suchetha Nambanoor Kunnath , Matteo Cancellieri , Petr Knoth CORE, The Open University, United Kingdom Identifying and extracting Data Access Statements from full-text academic articles Matteo Cancellieri , David Pride , Petr Knoth Open University, United Kingdom Laying the Groundwork for the Future: Creating Tools to Better Harness Metadata and Data Packages Peyton Carolynn Tvrdy National Transportation Library, United States of America Content-update Signaling and Alerting Protocol (CUSAP) Craig Van Dyck ¹ , Patrick Hargitt ² , Constanze Schelhorn ³ 1: Solutions Spectrum, LLC; 2: Atypion; 3: MDPI	Repository Showdown 1 Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Leigh Stork , University of Strathclyde Figshare Andrew Mckenna-Foster Figshare, United States of America Archipelago Commons: blooms, new growth and healthy trees from the community garden. Diego Alberto Pino Navarro , Allison Sherrick Metropolitan New York Library Council, United States of America Repository Showdown: Dataverse Gustavo Durand Harvard University, United States of America Introducing Fedora - The flexible, modular, open-source repository platform for long-term digital preservation Arran Griffith , Dan Field Fedora Repository Showdown: DSpace Maureen Walsh ¹ , Pascal Becker ² , Andrea Bollini ³ , Ignace Deroost ⁴ , lanthe Sutherland ⁵ 1: The Ohio State University Libraries, United States of America; 2: The Library Code, Berlin, Germany; 3: 4Science, Rome, Italy; 4: Atmire, Leuven, Belgium; 5: The University of	Panel- Community-Driven Global Governance of the OpenAIRE Interoperability Guidelines: advancing sustainability, openness, and modernization Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Ellen Ramsey , University of Virginia Community-Driven Global Governance of the OpenAIRE Interoperability Guidelines: advancing sustainability, openness, and modernization Pedro Príncipe ¹ , André Vieira ¹ , Leonidas Pispiringas ² , Eloy Rodrigues ¹ , Natalia Manola ² , Paolo Manghi ² 1: University of Minho, Portugal; 2: OpenAIRE AMKE

	Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil	Edinburgh, Edinburgh, Scotland
		InvenioRDM: Twenty Years of Supporting Research with FAIR and Transparent Practices <u>Zacharias Zacharodimos</u> , Pablo Tamarit CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research), Switzerland
15:00 - 15:30	Coffee Break Location: Rogers Lobby	
15:30 - 16:30	Minute Madness Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Richard David Jones , Cottage Labs Convener: Maximilian Moser , TU Wien	
	TU Wien & OSTrails: Connecting services <u>Maximilian Moser</u> , Tomasz Miksa TU Wien, Austria	
	Growing Up with Open-Source: A Digital Library Story <u>Juliet L. Hardesty</u> Indiana University, United States of America	
	InvenioRDM features powering the EU Open Research Repository <u>Pablo Tamarit</u> ¹ , <u>Zacharias Zacharodimos</u> ¹ , Kristi Holmes ² 1: CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research), Switzerland; 2: Northwestern University, United States	
	Prim and Proper?: Exploring Best Practices for Useful Title Creation on Non-Text Digital Items <u>Megan Scott</u> , <u>Shelley Barba</u> Texas Tech University, United States of America	
	Reimagining DSpace Analytics: A Blue-Sky Approach to Accessible, Author-Centered Metrics <u>Franny Gaede</u> , <u>Catherine Flynn-Purvis</u> University of Oregon, United States of America	
	A Secure Hub for Access, Reliability, and Exchange of Data (SHARED) <u>Torsten Reimer</u> , H. Birali Runesha University of Chicago, United States of America	
	Enhancing Search in Digital Collections: Traditional vs. AI Keyword Searches <u>Quinn Sluzenski</u> , Jennifer Young Northwestern University Libraries, United States of America	
	Publishing datasets with JoDaKISS and Episciences overlay journals <u>Raphaël Tournoy</u> ¹ , Sibylle Hermann ² 1: CNRS - CCSD, France; 2: University of Stuttgart, Germany	
	Concepts of Visibility, findability, discoverability, SEO and ASEO in digital repositories. <u>Danilo Reyes-Lillo</u> ¹ , Cristófol Rovira ¹ , Alejandro Morales-Vargas ² 1: Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Spain; 2: Universidad de Chile, Chile	
	Exploring ETD Embargo Policies: Survey Results and Practical Guidance for Repository Managers <u>Emily Johnson</u> ¹ , <u>Shelley Barba</u> ² 1: University of Texas at San Antonio, United States of America; 2: Texas Tech University, United States of America	
	Fostering good practices at the Cultural Heritage Open Scholarship Network (CHOSN) <u>Ilkay Holt</u> , Susan Miles, Nora Ramsey British Library, United Kingdom	

Improving Research Availability in Low-Bandwidth Areas: Eprints3v5 Bundle Export

Edward Oakley

EPrints Services, University of Southampton, United Kingdom

New Work Types are Here: Expanded ORCID Metadata Schema based on COAR

Brian Minihan, Tom Demeranville

ORCID, Inc., United States of America

PHAIDRA: A Journey Towards Scalable Open Repositories

Eva D. Gergely, Raman Ganguly

University of Vienna, Austria

Plucking and Re-planting ORCIDs in Data Repository Datasets: Readme Harvesting for Metadata Improvement

Kent T Gerber

University of Minnesota Libraries, United States of America

Leveraging ReCiter to identify articles, notify authors, and facilitate deposition of manuscripts into Cornell's eCommons

Drew Wright, Paul Albert

Weill Cornell Medicine, United States of America

Toward accessible PDF documents in Open Access Repositories

Alexa Ramirez Vega

Instituto Tecnológico de Costa Rica, Costa Rica

Digital Repositories in the Arab World: Status, Challenges, and Future Prospects

Sherine Mahmoud Eid

Bibliotheca Alexandrina, Egypt

Helping to preserve and share Oaxaca's history

Lisa Lamont, Matt Ferrill

San Diego State University, United States of America

Bridging the Gap: Developing Open Digital Repositories for Namibian Cultural Heritage

Tertu Ponhele Haihwa, Sylvia Umana, Liina Kamenye

Namibia University of Science Technology, Namibia

COAR Resource Type Vocabulary - Enhancing Interoperability Across the Repository Ecosystem

Kathleen Shearer¹, Isabel Bernal², Ellen Ramsey¹

1: COAR, Netherlands, The; 2: CSIC, Spain

Nice DSpace

Brian Keese

Indiana University Libraries, United States of America

Powering Institutional Repository Growth with OA Switchboard

Emily Bongiovanni, Katie Behrman, Jonathan Kiritharan

Carnegie Mellon University, United States of America

Open Access Repositories Tracking Project

Petr Knoth, Matteo Cancellieri, David Pride

CORE, The Open University, United Kingdom

Rescuing Legacy Data: Using Optical Character Recognition Technologies to Make Airline Consumer Data Accessible

PeytonCarolynn Tvrdy

National Transportation Library, United States of America

Engaging a City's History through Consortial Search

Jessica BrodeFrank

Chicago Collections Consortium, United States of America

An attempt to create a sustainable data repository and CRIS using a bespoke application

Kosuke Tanabe

National Institute for Materials Science

Wicked? Or Popular?: It's Time to Try Configuring Entities

Anne Shelley

Iowa State University, United States of America

**16:30 -
18:30**

Poster Session and Welcome Reception

Location: [Rogers Lobby](#)

Date: Tuesday, 17/June/2025

<p>08:00 - 17:00</p>	<p>Registration Location: Rogers Lobby</p>				
<p>09:00 - 10:30</p>	<p>Presentations- Advocacy and the Human Touch Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Jenny Evans, University of Westminster</p> <p>Our Common Cause: Advocating for Human Labor for Outreach, Technical Expertise, and the future of Institutional Repositories Grace Swinnerton, Dylan Mohr Syracuse University Libraries, United States of America</p>	<p>Presentations- Repository challenges and opportunities Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Richard William Fyson, CoSector, University of London</p> <p>Towards a Plan S compliant repository: Building a safe and sustainable haven for scholarly content. Frank Diepmaat¹, Maarten Leenders¹, Bram Luyten² 1: Tilburg University; 2: Atmire</p>	<p>Lightning (24x7)- Communities Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Chinwe Veronica Anunobi, National Library of Nigeria Convener: Lazarus Matzirofa, University of the Witwatersrand</p> <p>You Can't Force a Community: Trusting Your Instinct in Digital Collection Partnerships Pamela Pierce Oregon Health & Science University, United States of America</p>	<p>Panel- Managing Access to Open Repositories in the Age of Generative AI Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Torsten Reimer, University of Chicago</p> <p>Managing Access to Open Repositories in the Age of Generative AI Matteo Cancellieri¹, Martin Klein², George Macgregor³, Kathleen Shearer⁴, Allison Sherrick⁵, Petr Knoth¹ 1: CORE, The Open University, United Kingdom; 2: Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL); 3: The University of Glasgow; 4: Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR); 5: Metropolitan New York Library Council</p>	<p>Developer Track Session 2 Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Kathryn Cassidy, Trinity College Dublin</p> <p>The IRD: Improving knowledge about the state of the repository system landscape through automated curation processes Paul Walk Antleaf Ltd., United Kingdom</p>
<p>Better Together: Growing Digital Repositories through Community-building and Collaboration Carmen Mitchell¹, David Walker², Andrew Weiss³, Michaela Bettez⁴, Dana Ospina⁵ 1: California State University San Marcos, United States of America; 2: California State University Office of the Chancellor; 3: California State University Northridge; 4: California State University Fullerton; 5: California State University Dominguez Hills</p>	<p>Towards a National CRIS: Building and Perspectives for Open Science in the Dominican Republic Manuel Made, Elsi Jimenez Instituto Tecnologico de Santo Domingo (INTEC), Dominican Republic, Open Science Caribbean (OSCaribbean)</p>	<p>Longitudinal growth and use of Open Repositories in the U.S. since 2015 Jimmy S Ghaphery Virginia Commonwealth University, United States of America</p>	<p>From Open Archive to Multifaceted Platform: Reconciling the Diverse Stakeholders Needs in HAL Nathalie Fargier, Bénédicte Kuntziger CNRS-CCSD, France</p>	<p>Repository Insights with OpenSearch Terrence W Brady California Digital Library, United States of America</p>	
<p>Automating depositing research to the institutional repository and reshaping the 'call to action' for authors Ruth Mallalieu, Jason Partridge University of Oxford, United Kingdom</p>	<p>404 not found – Approaches for Ensuring the Sustainable Management of Living Resources apart from Data Repositories in the Digital Humanities Patrick Helling Data Center for the Humanities (DCH), University of Cologne, Germany</p>	<p>Why and how the TRUST Principles for digital repositories are used Meredith P. Goins^{1,2} 1: World Data System, United States of America; 2: University of Tennessee, Knoxville</p>	<p>Integrating Digital Repositories and Learning Management Systems using EduLink Corey Halpin University of Wisconsin - Madison, United States of America</p>	<p>Automated Data Analytics: A Statistical Dashboard Built with GitLab CI/CD for a Data Repository Based on CKAN Li Fang Wang¹, Cheng-Jen Lee², Tyng-Ruey Chuang² 1: National Cheng Kung University, Taiwan; 2: Academia Sinica, Taiwan</p>	
<p>Empowering Community Voices Kyle Morgan Cal Poly Humboldt, United States of</p>	<p>Conundrums of Open Repositories: Challenges in Establishing a Collaborative Framework for Digitizing Medieval Manuscript Collections Across the Midwestern United States Michelle Dalmau, Julie Hardesty,</p>	<p>Cost-benefit of open research infrastructures: the case of the Portuguese repositories network RCAAP Pedro Príncipe¹, Antónia Correia¹,</p>			

	America	Sudha Anand Indiana University Bloomington, United States of America	Paulo Lopes², Louis Colnot³, Jessica Catalano³ 1: University of Minho, Portugal; 2: FCT- FCCN; 3: CSIL		
			Preserving Our Past, Securing Our Future for Inclusivity: A Nigerian Perspective on Route To Digital Contents Sustainability Chinwe Anunobi, Chukwuemeka Udoji National Library of Nigeria, Nigeria		
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break Location: Rogers Lobby				
11:00 - 12:30	Presentations- Software: repositories, metadata and citations Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Joseph Kraus , Colorado School of Mines Exploring global academic repositories for software. Domhnall Carlin Queen's University Belfast, United Kingdom A Repository for Preserving and Managing Running Applications Raman Ganguly University of Vienna, Austria Enhancing Metadata Workflows and Long-Term Preservation of Research Outputs: Adopting FAIR Principles with Dagstuhl Publishing Saadet Bozaci, Michael Didas, Michael Wagner Schloss Dagstuhl Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik GmbH, Germany Promoting Visibility into Collections through Object Analysis	Presentations- Sharing Repositories and Resources Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Adrian Ho , University of Chicago Building a Sustainable Open Repository Network: The Launch of Open Repositories Ireland (ORI) Christopher Loughnane¹, Cillian Joy¹, Caleb Derven² 1: University of Galway, Ireland; 2: University of Limerick The Big Picture: Visualizing Networks in the Shared Research Repository Nora Ramsey British Library, United Kingdom The Expanding and Overlapping Roles of Institutional and Generalist Repositories: Building an Interoperable Data Repository Ecosystem Together Matthew Carson¹, Lisa Curtin², Aaron Doran³, Pearl Go⁴, Sara Gonzales⁵, Ben Gorham⁶, Maria Guerreiro⁷, Clarke Iakovakis⁸, Matthew	Repository Showdown 2 Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Leigh Stork , University of Strathclyde Hyku Heather Greer Klein¹, Nic Don Stanton- Roark² 1: Samvera, United States of America; 2: Private Academic Library Network of Indiana (PALNI), Towards EPrints 3.5: repository developments, roadmap, and governance improvements Justin Bradley¹, Will Fyson², George Macgregor³, Rory McNicholl¹, Tomasz Neugebauer⁴, Kate Petherbridge⁵, Edward Oakley¹, John Salter⁶ 1: EPrints Services, University of Southampton, UK; 2: CoSector, University of London, UK; 3: University of Glasgow, UK; 4: Concordia University, Canada; 5: University of York, UK; 6: University of Leeds, UK Repository Showdown: Islandora Noah Smith, Aubrey Shanahan Islandora Foundation,	Presentations- DSpace 1 Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Ianthe Sutherland , University of Edinburgh Towards enriched open scholarly information: integrating DSpace repositories and OpenAlex Agustina Martinez Garcia¹, Andrea Bollini², Susanna Mornati² 1: University of Cambridge, United Kingdom; 2: 4Science Deep Integration of GND with DSpace's External Sources Framework: A Case Study of Authority Data Utilization Pascal-Nicolas Becker, Kim Michael Shepherd The Library Code, Germany Bridging Communities: Vireo and DSpace Integration for Open Knowledge Sharing Alexa Hight¹, Christopher Starcher², Colleen Lyon³, Emily Johnson⁴ 1: Texas State University; 2: Texas Tech University; 3:	

<p>Eric Lopatin California Digital Library, United States of America</p>	<p>Mariner⁹, Kristi Holmes¹⁰, Marcy Vana¹¹, Julie Wood¹² 1: Northwestern University; 2: Figshare; 3: Elsevier - Mendeley Data; 4: Northwestern University; 5: Northwestern University; 6: Case Western Reserve University; 7: Dryad; 8: Oklahoma State University; 9: University of Rochester; 10: Northwestern University; 11: Washington University in St. Louis; 12: Vivli</p> <p>Ensuring the Future of Digital Repositories in West and Central Africa: A Case Study on BAOBAB and Sustainable Repository Development Wisdom Sefakor Ankora West And Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN), Ghana</p>	<p>United States of America</p> <p>Hyrax Nicholas Homenda Tufts University, United States of America</p> <p>Open Science Framework (OSF) Gretchen Gueguen Center for Open Science, United States of America</p> <p>Avalon Media System Jon Brandon Cameron Indiana University Libraries, United States of America</p>	<p>University of Texas; 4: University of Texas at San Antonio</p> <p>DSpace 9.0 and Beyond: What's next for DSpace Tim Donohue, Holger Lenz Lyrasis, United States of America</p>	
<p>12:30 - 13:30</p>	<p>Lunch Break Location: Rogers Lobby</p>			
<p>13:30 - 14:30</p>	<p>Panel- Software dies, data should be forever: OCFL as a software agnostic storage approach Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Rachael Kotarski, University of Chicago</p>			
<p>13:30 - 15:00</p>	<p>Software dies, data should be forever: OCFL as a software agnostic storage approach Simeon Warner¹, Rosalyn Metz², Neil Jefferies³, Becky Andresen⁴, Dustin Slater⁵, Andrew Woods⁶, Tom Wrobel³ 1: Cornell University; 2: Emory University; 3: University of Oxford; 4: University of Wisconsin - Madison; 5: University of Texas at Austin; 6: Harvard University</p>			
<p>13:30 - 15:00</p>	<p>Presentations- AI and Repositories Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Lazarus Matizirofa, University of the Witwatersrand</p> <p>A Data Curation, Interrogation, and Access System for the Texas Robotics DataVerse Xingru Zhou, Zhiyun Deng, Yao-Cheng Chan, Sadanand Modak, Maria Esteva University of Texas at Austin, United States of America</p> <p>Can this robot query my Linked Data Store? Exploring retrieval-augmented models for Repository Search &</p>	<p>Lightning (24x7)- Repository tools and developments Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Aileen O'Carroll, Digital Repository of Ireland</p> <p>Implementing UN SDG Auto-Tagging: A Practical Guide for Librarians Kyle Morgan Cal Poly Humboldt, United States of America</p> <p>A Flexible Workspace: Using the Cloud to Stage & Ingest New Content Eric Lopatin California Digital Library, United States of America</p>	<p>Presentations- Provider Communities Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Maureen Walsh, The Ohio State University</p> <p>The Fedora Community finds its future path by learning from the past and bringing others together. Arran Griffith, Dan Field Fedora/Lyrasis, Canada</p> <p>Balancing the Global and the Local at the Research Organization Registry (ROR) Amanda French</p>	<p>Presentations- Data Repositories 2 Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Emily Bongiovanni, Carnegie Mellon University</p> <p>Development Of An Integrated Lifecycle Of RDM Tools For Data Publication: Looking Back And Forward @ KU Leuven Dieuwertje Bloemen, Ingrid Barcena Roig KU Leuven, Belgium</p> <p>Scaling Up: Expanding Data Repository Support for Growth in Large Datasets Michael Shensky¹,</p>

<p>Discovery Kirsta Stapelfeldt, Bennett Steinburg, Natkeeran Ledchumykanthan, Kyle Huynh University of Toronto</p>	<p>Integrating IIF annotations in DSpace Andrea Bollini, Claudio Cortese 4Science, Italy</p>	<p>Crossref, United States of America</p>	<p>Courtney Mumma², Laura Sare³, Robert Kalescky⁴, Millicent Weber⁵, Bryan Gee¹ 1: University of Texas at Austin, United States of America; 2: Texas Digital Library; 3: Texas A&M University; 4: Southern Methodist University; 5: Baylor University</p>	
<p>Integrating Machine Actionable Data Management and Sharing Plans (maDMSP) into Campus-Based Open Research and Repository Workflows: A Case Study from the University of Colorado Boulder Aditya N. Ranganath, Andrew M. Johnson University of Colorado Boulder, United States of America</p>	<p>Sustainable Development Goals in EPrints: Updates, Failures, and Experiments Eleanor Dumbill CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom</p>	<p>USRN Discovery Pilot: Increasing the Discoverability of Open Access Content Through a National Network Petr Knoth¹, Paul Walk², Matteo Cancellieri¹, Michael Upshall¹, Halyna Torchylo¹, Jennifer Beamer³, Kathleen Shearer⁴, Heather Joseph³ 1: CORE, The Open University; 2: Antleaf; 3: Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR); 4: SPARC</p>	<p>Toward a Comprehensive Research Data Catalog at Texas A&M University James Creel Texas A&M University, United States of America</p>	
<p>We Need to Chat: A presentation about real-world AI use cases Michael Klein Northwestern University Libraries, United States of America</p>	<p>AI as a Responsible Partner in FAIR Metadata Creation: Lessons Learned Jenny Li University of Michigan Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research, United States of America</p>			
	<p>How do you describe software in record metadata? Matteo Cancellieri, Petr Knoth Open University, United Kingdom</p>			
<p>15:00 - 15:30</p>	<p>Coffee Break Location: Rogers Lobby</p>			
<p>15:30 - 16:30</p>	<p>Panel- Recognizing Software as a Critical Component in Open Science: Advancing an Interoperable, Community-Driven Vision for Infrastructures Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Richard David Jones, Cottage Labs</p> <p>Recognizing Software as a Critical Component in Open Science: Advancing an Interoperable, Community-Driven Vision for Infrastructures Morane Gruenpeter¹, Yannick Barborini², Saadet Bozacci³, Raphaël Tournoy², Daniel S. Katz⁴ 1: Software Heritage, Inria; 2: CCSD / CNRS; 3: Schloss Dagstuhl – LZI, Publishing; 4: University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign</p>			
<p>15:30 - 17:00</p>	<p>Presentations- DSpace 2 Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Ilanthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh</p> <p>From Load Times to Bot Traffic: A Comprehensive Approach to DSpace Performance Ignace Deroost, Art Lowel, Yura Bondarenko, Lieven Droogmans Atmire, Belgium</p> <p>Transitioning</p>	<p>Presentations- Repository Retrospectives Location: N110- Orchestra Room Convener: Ilkay Holt, British Library</p> <p>17 years of PHAIDRA at the University of Vienna. Opportunities and challenges of managing an open repository at a large and heterogeneous university. Susanne Blumesberger</p>	<p>Presentations- Repository Governance, Ethics and Curation Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Kristi Park, Texas Digital Library, USA</p> <p>The Governance of Open Repository Programs: Progress and Possibilities Maureen Walsh The Ohio State University Libraries, United States of America</p>	<p>Presentations- PIDs and Harvesting Location: C119&121- Classrooms Convener: Adrian Ho, University of Chicago</p> <p>The Decentralized Archival Resource Key (dARK) - from a Proof of Concept to a Service Implementation in the Brazilian Open Science Ecosystem Washington Luis Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo¹, Lautaro Julian Matas², J. Edilson Filho¹,</p>

<p>Repositories: From EPrints to DSpace CRIS – The Case of the Zurich Open Repository and Archive (ZORA)</p> <p><u>Martin Brändle</u>¹, <u>Lukasz Nowak</u>², <u>Piotr Masalski</u>², <u>Lukasz Wawer</u>², <u>Mateusz Adamiak</u>²</p> <p>1: University of Zurich, Switzerland; 2: PCG Academia, Poland</p>	<p>University of Vienna, Austria</p> <p>Three Repositories Walk into a Library: recapping 30 years of repository development at Duke University Libraries</p> <p><u>Jennifer Jordan</u>, <u>Maggie Dickson</u></p> <p>Duke University Libraries, United States of America</p>	<p>An Integrated Open Ecosystem: Whose Responsibility Is it?</p> <p><u>Bridget Almas</u>¹, <u>Sheila Rabun</u>¹, <u>Michele Mennielli</u>¹, <u>Paolo Gujilde</u>¹, <u>Jennifer Beamer</u>², <u>Sarala Wimalaratne</u>³, <u>Jon Dunn</u>⁴, <u>Kate Dohe</u>⁵, <u>Agustina Martinez Garcia</u>⁶</p> <p>1: Lyrasis; 2: California State University San Bernardino; 3: DataCite; 4: Indiana University; 5: University of Maryland; 6: University of Cambridge, United Kingdom</p>	<p>Márcio Gurgel do Amaral¹, Gabriel Marques¹, Thiago Nóbrega³</p> <p>1: Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; 2: Red Latinoamericana para la Ciencia Abierta (LA Referencia), Spain; 3: Universidade Federal de Campina Grande (UFCCG), Brazil</p>
<p>DASH Stories: Implementing a qualitative feedback service in DSpace 8</p> <p><u>Colin Lukens</u>¹, <u>Grace Dunbar</u>¹, <u>Andrea Bollini</u>²</p> <p>1: Harvard University, United States of America; 2: 4Science, Italy</p>	<p>Advancing Open Science: Transforming UFPR'S Digital Repository Infrastructure</p> <p><u>Karolayne Costa Rodrigues de Lima</u>, <u>Paula Carina de Araújo</u>, <u>Marcos Sfair Sunye</u></p> <p>Federal University of Paraná, Brazil</p>	<p>The Case for a National Repository of Policing Data in the United States</p> <p><u>Cheryl Danton</u>¹, <u>Christopher Graziul</u>¹, <u>Elliott Ramos</u>²</p> <p>1: University of Chicago, United States of America; 2: CBS News</p>	<p>The Utility of PIDs in Harvesting Open Data Repositories: Challenges in Operating a National Data Discovery Service</p> <p><u>Tristan K Kuehn</u></p> <p>Digital Research Alliance of Canada, Canada</p>
<p>Reimagining a trusted institutional repository: transforming EPFL's Infoscience with DSpace-CRIS</p> <p><u>Jorge Rodrigues de Matos</u>, <u>Julien Sicot</u></p> <p>EPFL, Digital repositories and archives - Library, Switzerland</p>	<p>Going deeper: the case for multiple repositories at UChicago</p> <p><u>Rachael Kotarski</u></p> <p>University of Chicago, United States of America</p>	<p>Scenarios Motivating Integration and Re-Curation</p> <p><u>Martin Halbert</u>¹, <u>Ted Habermann</u>², <u>Jamaica Jones</u>³</p> <p>1: University of North Carolina at Greensboro, United States of America; 2: Metadata Game Changers, United States of America; 3: University of Pittsburgh, United States of America</p>	<p>Analysis of Requirements and Solutions for Issuing Persistent Identifiers (DOIs) in the Brazilian Repository of Biodiversity - SiBBR</p> <p><u>Laura Vilela Rodrigues Rezende</u>¹, <u>Geisa Muller de Campos Ribeiro</u>¹, <u>Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro</u>¹, <u>Cassia Oliveira</u>¹, <u>Fabiano Couto Corrêa da Silva</u>², <u>Carolina Howard Felicissimo</u>³</p> <p>1: Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil; 2: Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil; 3: Rede Nacional de Pesquisa, Brazil</p>

17:30 - 22:00

Conference Dinner on the Spirit of Chicago- prior registration required

Date: Wednesday, 18/June/2025

08:30 - 14:00	Registration Location: Rogers Lobby			
09:00 - 10:30	<p>Presentations- Research Data Preservation Location: Griffin Auditorium Convener: Joseph Kraus, Colorado School of Mines</p> <p>From Legacy to Leadership: Transforming OLCF's Data Repository for the Future of Open Scientific Data Olga Anna Kuchar¹, Joshua Brown¹, Tirthankar Ghosal¹, Meghan Berry¹, Patrick Widener¹, Tatiyanna Singleton¹, Michael Tharp¹, Keith Kawasaki² 1: Oak Ridge National Laboratory, United States of America; 2: CivicActions</p> <p>Advancing Data Stewardship: Developing a Research Data Retention Policy at the Texas Data Repository Santi Thompson¹, Michael Shensky², Millicent Weber³, Christina Chan-Park³, Laura Sare⁴, Andrea Schorr⁵, Xuan Zhou⁶ 1: University of Houston, United States of America; 2: University of Texas at Austin, United States of America; 3: Baylor University, United States of America; 4: Texas A&M University, United States of America; 5: University of Texas Health San Antonio, United States of America; 6: Texas State University, United States of America</p>	<p>Lightning (24x7) - Repository possibilities Location: N112- Band Room Convener: Ellen Ramsey, University of Virginia</p> <p>It doesn't have to be this way: Reimagining Institutional Repositories in-Transition Joe Kohlburn, Marcella Lees Southern Illinois University Edwardsville, United States of America</p> <p>Wikidata and repositories: opening up the future David Fiore Saint Mary's College, United States of America</p> <p>Diamond Open Access: Repositories as journal publishing platforms, practical experiences Peter Sutton-Long, Agustina Martínez García University of Cambridge</p> <p>Possibilities for Accessible Repositories: a Case Study in ADA Title II Implementation Sarah Barsness, Erik Moore University of Minnesota, United States of America</p> <p>Barriers to the institutional repository network: how far is integration possible? Gareth Cole¹, Paul Stokes² 1: Loughborough University, United Kingdom; 2: Jisc</p> <p>Simplifying Data Curation Through Tooling And Automation Dieuwertje Bloemen, Ozgur Karadeniz KU Leuven, Belgium</p>	<p>Presentations- COAR Notify Location: C116- Community Gathering Room Convener: Elizabeth Krzrnarich, University of Wisconsin</p> <p>Using PCI, COAR Notify and EPrints to Re-Invent the Publication Workflow Will Fyson, Rory McNicholl CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom</p> <p>Impacts on the Repository of COAR Notify, and tools to help you Richard David Jones Cottage Labs, United Kingdom</p> <p>Interoperable verification and dissemination of software assets in repositories using COAR Notify Matteo Cancellieri¹, Martin Docekal², David Pride¹, Morane Gruenpeter³, David Douard³, Petr Knoth¹ 1: Open University, United Kingdom; 2: Brno University of Technology; 3: Software Heritage</p> <p>Moving repositories out of the periphery and into the center of scholarly publishing Kathleen Shearer¹, Eloy Rodrigues², Paul Walk³, Martin Klein⁴, Tamy Nakano¹ 1: COAR, Netherlands; 2: University of Minho, Portugal; 3: Antleaf LTD, UK; 4: Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, US</p>	<p>Developer Track Session 3 Location: C119&121-Classrooms Convener: Maximilian Moser, TU Wien</p> <p>Leveraging AI Programming Assistants for Digital Repository Development: A Practical Demonstration Hui Zhang Oregon State University Libraries and Press, United States of America</p> <p>Unraveling the Mystery of DSpace Backend Failures: A Debugging Journey Jozef Misutka, Milan Majchrák dataquest s.r.o., Slovakia</p> <p>Building Flexible, AI-Powered Forms for Repositories with react-formule Miguel García García, Pamfilos Fokianos, Antonios Papadopoulos CERN, Switzerland</p> <p>Automating Data Imports in a DSpace-CRIS's Institutional Repository Jorge Rodrigues de Matos, Julien Sicot EPFL, Switzerland</p>
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break Location: Rogers Lobby			
11:00 - 11:50	Keynote speaker Ben Zhao Location: Griffin Auditorium Ben Zhao is Neubauer Professor of Computer Science at University of Chicago. He is a Fellow of the ACM, a TED/AI speaker, and was recently named to TIME Magazine's AI/100, 100 most influential people in AI. He has spent the last 3 years building tools that shield visual artists (and other creatives) from non-consensual training and image mimicry.			
11:50 - 12:30	Closing Plenary Location: Griffin Auditorium			
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch Break Location: Rogers Lobby			

